

A Comparative Study of Students' Academic Performance in English Language in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory

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Abstract

This research comparatively studied students' academic performance in English Language in public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory. The research design adopted was descriptive and ex-post facto surveys. Three research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. Questionnaire titled, Comparative Study of Students' Academic Performance in English Language in Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools (CSAPEL), and data on record were the instruments used. The sample size was 380 and 370 students, as well as 1865 and 1734 data of students in public and private senior secondary schools respectively. Data analysis was by mean score, standard deviation and t-test statistics. Findings indicated that teaching aids/facilities have influence on students' academic performance in English Language, teacher qualification has influence on students' academic performance in English Language in public and private senior secondary schools, and private senior secondary school students perform better in English Language. Based on the findings, the recommendations proposed are that government and school proprietors should make concerted efforts to ensure that teaching aids/facilities are provided, government should ensure that only individuals with the requisite qualification in English Language are employed both in public and private schools.

Keywords: Students, English Language, Academic Performance, Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools

Introduction

The importance of English Language in learning cannot be overemphasized and its relevance made the federal government to accord prominence to the teaching and learning of the subject in Nigerian schools (FRN, 2004). Learning has been so much associated with the school that some people almost think that learning goes on only in schools and the medium of instruction (learning) in Nigeria is the English Language (Ibrahim, Anka & Yabo, 2017). There is no doubting the fact that much learning goes on in school, and the schools are particularly and specifically

arranged so as to facilitate effective learning. Unfortunately, the poor condition of the schools, particularly the secondary schools today in the nation raises a lot of anxiety. A cursory look at these schools in spite of government efforts reveals that schools are dominated by dilapidated buildings, void of good furniture and equipment, schools where instructional materials are either not provided or are grossly inadequate; schools that are under-staffed; schools, where teachers' salaries and allowances are not promptly paid, schools that have not been inspected for the last 15 years; schools where there is no discipline among other things.

The government and especially the parents are very much concerned with the quality and volume of learning acquired by their children, wards and citizens as this is related to the quality and quantity of the contribution which the individual can make to his immediate family, community and the nation as a whole. The quality of education that is imparted to the youth and the precedence given to education largely contributes to attitude formation of the youths. So whatever kind of seed sown in the classroom; the manner in which it is nurtured and the strength which it imbibes in its various stages of growth will all determine the harvest that the nation will reap in the form of its educated youth coming out of the schools, colleges and universities. The imprints of these institutions of learning will create indelible marks clearly visible in all fields of the national life; be it a clerk in an office, a soldier in the battle field, a school master in a village school, a university professor, a bureaucrat running the administration in a seat of power. This great impact of education on the national character is understandable once it is recognized, both the short term as well as long term power education wields over all who go through its process. Historical evidence proves that nations were made or unmade, battles lost and won, revolution wrought, so much so that entire empires collapsed or emerged due to the educational systems of various peoples of the World. Ancient Greece and Rome at the peak of their political glory were also the seats of learning and a source of intellectual guidance and inspiration for the entire known world, but when intellectual decadence struck, it attacked the very fabric of society (Harris & Sass, 2008). This means the onus now falls on academics and researchers to embark on research and development strategy to favour secondary education in the context of Nigeria's current reality and harsh economic environment. This will be feasible with the necessary provision of school facilities to enhance teaching and learning of the subject.

School facilities have been observed as a potent factor to qualitative education, and their importance to teaching and learning cannot be over-emphasized. According to Ogbu (2015), instructional facilities include conducive classrooms, English Language laboratory, a well-stocked library, contemporary English Language textbooks, and language equipment. Tahir (2003) averred that instructional facilities are physical and spatial enablers that enhance teaching and learning in the classroom. The study of Iroegbu (2020) revealed that there is significant difference in academic achievement of students in English Language based on school facilities. The study of Mogaka (2019) also found out that facilities such as course books and set books, classrooms and libraries equally have significant influence on students' academic performance in English Language.

However, the rate of poor academic performance of students in Nigeria had resulted to economic and social wastage and this has become a great concern to all stakeholders in education.

For instance, in 2008, 25.94% of the students had credits pass in English Language. The year 2009 was another year of poor result across the nation (Adeiza, 2011). Feng and Sass (2010) believed that teacher and students' interaction in the classroom depends on the level of teacher's qualification and experience, which brings about easy communication and thereby enhancing the performance of students. More also, the findings of Popoola and Olubunmi (2013), as well as Adepoju and Oluchukwu (2016) revealed that there was a marked difference in the performance of students in urban and rural schools in senior secondary certificate examination.

There is no doubt that there has been tremendous development in the educational sector of the country. New public and private schools have been established to meet the educational demand of its citizens. However, there has been an increasing concern about the overall academic performance of public and private secondary school students as measured by the results released by the National Examinational Council (NECO) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSSCE). Therefore, this study is an attempt to carry out a comparative study of students' academic performance in English Language in public and private senior secondary schools in the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Abraham Maslow theory of motivation and the theory of learning which was championed by Benjamin Bloom (1948). Abraham Maslow wrote an article in 1943 titled, "**Theory of Human Motivation**", which appeared in Psychological Review. This was later expanded in his book, "Toward a Psychology of Being". Maslow attempted to formulate a needs-based framework of human motivation. Motivation is a goal-directed behaviour. Motivation can be improved through encouraging feedback, receiving assistance from expert and non-expert models, and achieving successful experiences. The six C's of motivation, as coined by Turner and Paris include choice, challenge, control, collaboration, constructing meaning, and consequences. Students' motivation increases by choosing a meaningful project that is feeling-related and value-related.

On the other hand, Benjamin Bloom organized a group of educators in 1948, who, over a period of eight years, classified educational goals and objectives into what they referred to as Bloom's Taxonomy. This Taxonomy is categorized into three domains of learning: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor: the cognitive domain dwells on the mental ability of the individual and it is sub-divided into six sequential levels of thinking. The first three levels or lower-order skills include: remembering, understanding and applying. The last three levels or higher-order skills include: analyzing, evaluating and creating; affective domain focuses on the learner's attitudes, motivation, and values. The levels and types of learning in the affective domain are classified into five areas: receiving/attending; responding; valuing; conceptualizing/organizing; and characterizing by value; the psychomotor reflects expressly on the ability to use tool of learning for manipulative purposes.

This study is anchored on this subject based on the fact that when individual students are intrinsically or extrinsically motivated to learn English Language, they will tend to put in extra efforts in the subject, and they will not develop any apathy. More also, the emphasis on learning

borders on how students could easily remember, understand, apply, analyze, evaluate and create meaning out of what they have been taught in English Language so that the knowledge gained in the subject can be used to explain and express other subjects they are taught, being the language of instruction in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to comparatively evaluate students' academic performance in English Language in public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- i. Compare the extent of influence of teaching aids/facilities on students' academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory;
- ii. Compare the extent of influence of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory;
- iii. Compare the trend in students' academic performance in English Language in SSCE between public and private senior secondary schools between 2014 and 2019.

Research Questions

The following research questions served as guide to this study:

1. What is the extent of influence of teaching aids/facilities on students' academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory?
2. What is the extent of influence of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory?
3. What is the trend in students' academic performance in English Language in SSCE between public and private senior secondary schools between 2014 and 2019?

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis served as guide to this study:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of senior secondary school students in public schools and academic performance of senior secondary school students in private schools.

Method

The research approach adopted in this study is descriptive and ex-post facto surveys. According to FCT education baseline survey (2019), there were 62 public and 46 private Senior Secondary Schools in the FCT. The population of students in both public and private Senior secondary schools were 31,957 and 10,384 respectively. Also between the period of 2014 to 2019, students that sat for SSCE were 54,184 and 18,650 for public and private senior secondary schools. Sample size for the study was 380 from public and 370 from private senior secondary schools.

These represent the samples the researchers could readily use in terms of time and available resources. The researchers developed a questionnaire called, “Comparative Study of Students’ Academic Performance in English Language in Public and Private Secondary Schools (CSAPEL) Questionnaire, as instrument for data collection. Also, records of academic performance of students in senior secondary schools for five academic sessions were sought from the schools that participated in the study. CSAPEL consisted of two sections A and B. Section A solicited information on the personal data of students while section B contains a four-point Linkert scale ten item questionnaire developed by the researchers. The questionnaire items were arranged in two sub-headings to seek information on the variables being studied. The instrument was given to two specialists in Educational Management for validation. Their corrections formed the basis of the final instrument used for the main study. To ensure content validity, a pilot test was carried out by administering the instrument to 60 students (30 from public and 30 from private schools) outside the study area. The test was calculated using Cronbach alpha to establish the reliability of the questionnaire, and the reliability coefficient of 0.86 and 0.77 were obtained. The mean rating of each questionnaire item was determined by scoring each response as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. Academic Performance in English Language was interpreted on the basis of Distinction = 4, Credit =3, Pass = 2 and fail = 1. Mean score of 2.5 and above implies an agreement with an item, while a mean value that was 2.49 and below signifies disagreement with an item on the questionnaire. The t-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis. P-value in relation to 0.05 level of significance was used to interpret the hypotheses. Where a p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but where a p-value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of influence of teaching aids/facilities on students academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory?

Table 1 shows the items on extent of influence of teaching aids/facilities from the research questionnaire.

Table 1: Extent of Influence of Teaching Aids/Facilities

	Public		Private		Decision
	\bar{x}	Sd	\bar{x}	Sd	
1. Conducive classrooms aids teaching and learning activities as well as performance.	3.02	0.82	3.11	0.92	Agree
2. Provision of English Language Laboratory enhance academic performance in oral English.	2.98	0.91	3.08	0.84	Agree
3. A well-stocked library with materials on English Language enhance performance.	3.04	0.93	3.13	0.90	Agree
4. Contemporary English Language textbooks and dictionaries enhance academic performances.	3.11	0.89	3.15	0.88	Agree
5. Digital recorders, audio-visuals, multi-media computers, language soft wares enhance performance in English Language.	3.09	0.90	3.09	0.68	Agree
	3.05	0.89	3.11	0.84	Accept

Table 1 showing questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, with mean scores of 3.02, 2.98, 3.04, 3.11 and 3.09 as well as 3.11, 3.08, 3.13, 3.15 and 3.09 respectively for public and private senior secondary schools show an agreement. In conclusion, the overall mean scores of 3.05 and 3.11 and standard deviation of 0.89 and 0.84 for both public and private schools implies that to a high extent, teaching aids/facilities have influence on students' academic performance in both public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of influence of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory?

Table 2 shows the items on the extent of influence of teachers' qualification from the research questionnaire.

Table 2: Extent of Influence of Teachers' Qualification

	Public		Private		Decision
	\bar{X}	Sd	\bar{X}	Sd	
6. A degree in English Language, i.e. BA (Ed) honours equips teachers to teach the subject better which enhance performance.	3.03	0.86	3.14	0.90	Agree
7. Possession of higher degree, e.g. Masters degree aids the teaching of the subject better to students.	3.01	0.9	3.12	0.84	Agree
8. Giving of clear guidance to students will be based on experience and ethical values of teaching.	3.14	0.89	3.00	0.82	Agree
9. Teachers with high quality do have long-lasting impression on the lives of the students which helps their performance.	3.06	0.77	3.11	0.80	Agree
10. Well qualified teachers manage classroom to enhance academic performance.	3.12	0.80	3.17	0.68	Agree
	3.07	0.84	3.11	0.81	Accept

Table 2 showing questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10, with mean scores of 3.03, 3.01, 3.14, 3.06 and 3.12 as well as 3.14, 3.12, 3.00, 3.11 and 3.17 respectively for public and private senior secondary schools show an agreement. In conclusion, the overall mean scores of 3.07 and 3.11 and standard deviation of 0.84 and 0.81 for both public and private schools implies that to a high extent, teachers' qualification have influence on students' academic performance in English Language in both public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory.

Research Question 3: What is the trend in students' academic performance in English Language in SSCE between public and private senior secondary schools between 2014 and 2019?

Tables 3 and 4 shows the items on trend in students' academic performance in SSCE as generated from the research questionnaire.

Table 3: Trend in Students' Academic Performance in English Language in Public Senior Secondary Schools

Sessions	Public Senior Secondary School Candidates						
	N	4	3	2	1	\bar{X}	Sd
2014/2015	370	137	167	55	11	3.16	0.80
2015/2016	370	144	170	37	19	3.19	0.88
2016/2017	375	135	184	41	15	3.17	0.84
2017/2018	375	146	191	30	8	3.27	0.89
2018/2019	375	150	165	45	15	3.20	0.86
	1865	712	877	208	68	3.20	0.85
		38%	47%	11%	4%		

Table 4: Trend in Students' Academic Performance in English Language in Private Senior Secondary Schools

Year	Private Senior Secondary School Candidates						
	N	4	3	2	1	\bar{X}	Sd
2014/2015	335	161	124	43	7	3.31	0.84
2015/2016	354	184	131	32	7	3.39	0.87
2016/2017	346	173	128	31	14	3.33	0.89
2017/2018	364	178	135	40	11	3.32	0.90
2018/2019	335	171	131	23	10	3.38	0.91
	1734	867	649	169	49	3.35	0.88
		50%	37%	10%	3%		

Tables 3 and 4 show the trend in students' academic performance in SSCE in English Language in public and private senior secondary schools between 2014 and 2019 respectively in Federal Capital Territory. From the table, the overall performance level shows that 38% of the students in public senior secondary schools had distinctions in mathematics, 47% had credit, 11% had pass and 4% failed, while 50% of the students in private senior secondary schools had distinction, 37% had credit, 10% had pass and 3% failed. This summarizes a 96% pass and 4% fail for public senior secondary schools and a 97% pass and 3% fail for private senior secondary schools. Also, details of the data analysis indicated that public secondary school students recorded highest performance in 2017/2018 academic session with mean score of 3.27 and least performance in 2014/2015 with mean score of 3.16, while the private secondary school students recorded highest performance in 2015/2016 with mean score of 3.39 and least performance in 2014/2015 with mean score of 3.31. Figure 2 presents a graphic picture of this analysis.

Hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of senior secondary school students in public schools and academic performance of senior secondary school students in private schools

Table 5: Difference in Students' Academic Performance in English Language in Public and Private Senior Secondary Schools.

Variables	\bar{x}	Sd	df	T	*p-value	Decision
Public	3.20	0.85				
			12	29.8	0.035	
Private	3.35	0.88				Significant

**(P<0.05 level of significance)*

Table 5 shows the results of the test of significant difference in trend in students' academic performance in SSCE in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory. The calculated t-value was 29.8. The p-value was 0.04, which is less than 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom = 12. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. In conclusion, this implies by the finding of the study that a significant difference exists in trend in students' academic performance in SSCE in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory.

Discussion

Analysis on table 3 indicated that the private senior secondary school students perform better than public senior secondary school students in English Language. This finding agrees with that of Popoola and Olubunmi (2013), as well as Adepaju and Oluchukwu (2016) who revealed that there was a marked difference in the performance of students in urban and rural schools in senior secondary certificate examination. Also, the test of hypothesis indicated that a significant difference exists in trend in students' academic performance in SSCE in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of this research, it was concluded that there is a significant difference in trend in students' academic performance in SSCE in English Language between public and private senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, implying that students in private senior secondary schools performed better than students in public senior secondary schools. This is due to the fact that teaching aids/facilities as well as teacher qualifications have significant influence on students' academic performance both in public and private senior secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the recommendations proposed are that: -

1. Government and private school proprietors should make concerted efforts to ensure that teaching aids/facilities are provided in schools, while the existing ones should be renovated periodically for the use of the students so that their academic performance in English Language will continually be enhanced.
2. Government and private school proprietors should ensure that only individuals with the requisite qualification in English Language are employed and retained in the service of the senior secondary schools so that they can continue to influence students' into having positive academic performance in English Language in secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory
3. Government and private schools' management should do more by ensuring that they do whatever that they need to do in order to enhance the teaching of English Language in senior secondary schools, as by so doing students can improve on their performance.

REFERENCES

- Adeiza, A. (2011). *Avoiding a repeat of mass failure in subsequent*. Retrieved 10/03/2020 from <http://www.peoplesdaily-online.com/news/education/2348>.
- Adepoju, T. L. & Oluchukwu, E. E. (2016). A study of secondary school students' academic performance at the senior school certificate examinations and implications for educational planning and policy in Nigeria. *Ethiopian International Multidisciplinary Journal*, 5(6), 314-333
- Education in FCT (2016). *Baseline survey of educational development in the Federal Capital Territory*. Retrieved 22/04/2020 from www.mdgfectabuja.net
- Feng L. & Sass, T.R. (2010). What makes special education teachers special? Teacher training and achievement of students with disabilities. CALDER Working Paper No. 49. Washington, D.C.: The Urban Institute.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National Policy on Education (Rev.)*. Lagos: NERC Press.
- Harris, D.N. & Sass, T.R. (2008). *Teacher training, teacher quality and student achievement*. CALDER Working Paper 3. Washington, D.C.: The Urban Institute.
- Ibrahim, F. A., Anka, S. M. & Yabo, N. U. (2017). *English as medium of instruction: Challenges to Nigerian primary schools*. Retrieved 10/03/2020 from <https://journals.sfu.ca>
- Iroegbu, E. E. (2020). School facilities, class size and academic achievement of secondary school students in English Language in Uyo Senatorial District, Akwalbom State. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(7), 38-45.

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- Josiah, O. & Oluwatoyin, K. B. (2017). Teacher quality as determinant of students' academic performance in secondary schools in Edo South Senatorial District of Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 5(13), 19-30.
- Mogaka, M. M. (2019). Availability of school facilities and their influence on students' academic achievement in public day secondary schools in Kisii County, Kenya. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 3(3), 451-455
- Ogbu, J. E (2015). Availability and utilization of instructional facilities of basic electricity in Ebonyi State technical colleges, *Developing Country Studies*, 5 (21), 125-137
- Ohia, A. N. (2019). Utilization of instructional facilities and the academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6 (2), 34-38
- Popoola, L. & Olubunmi, S. (2013). A correlated analysis of students' SSCE grade and performance in first year Use-of-English: A case study of Fountain University. *Osogbo. Journal of Languages and Culture*, 4(8), 150-154.
- Tahir, G (2003). *Basic education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers.
- Valerie, S. (2011). The 12 qualities of great teachers. Retrieved on 7/03/2020 from <http://www.washingtonpost.com/>